

Reimagining Femininity : The Role of Women in Anand Neelakantan's Novels

Paper Id : 19280 Submission Date : 2024-09-12 Acceptance Date : 2024-09-23 Publication Date : 2024-09-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13935267

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Abstract Anand Neelakantan's literary works present a modernized story setting where women's role exceeds traditional stereotypes, showcasing depth, influence and power. This abstract explores how Anand Neelakantan focuses on central female characters such as Sita, Kunti, Draupadi, Tara, and Shivagami. This study performs a subjective analysis to explore the detailed characterizations of female characters, focusing on their complex identities, standing against male-driven standards, and intersections with caste, class, and personal ambition. Neelakantan's female characters are seen as active and skilled in dealing with complicated social and political situations, often challenging traditional gender roles and showing their power in different ways. Their relationships, whether through alliances or conflicts, further enrich the narrative fabric, highlighting the importance of female solidarity and collaboration. Despite societal limitations, these women rise as moral leaders, driving change and impacting politics and emotions. Neelakantan's method questions old beliefs and offers fresh perspectives on old tales. His stories emphasize women's crucial roles, focusing on power, responsibilities, and gender roles

Keywords Antagonist Perspective, Gender Roles, Power and Influence, Social Challenge, Feminist interpretation, Subaltern View

Introduction Anand Neelakantan's fictional world challenges conventional narratives and highlights the unique and detailed stories of women through his female characters. In Neelakantan's novels, such as "Asura: Tale of the Vanquished" and "The Rise of Sivagami," women are not relegated to secondary roles or one-dimensional stereotypes but instead they are presented as dynamic individuals with influence, ambition and resilience. Neelakantan's stories about women encourage a closer look at their roles, how they are shown, and their complex lives in myths and historical stories. This study seeks to explore the methods through which Neelakantan challenges conventional gender norms, redefines femininity, and contributes to wider discussions on empowerment and representation in literature. If we talk about Feminism then it is a movement that supports equal rights for all genders and the upliftment of women. It helps us understand and interpret Indian stories like the Ramayana and the Mahabharata from a gender perspective. These old texts are based on traditional male-dominated ideas which offer rich opportunities to examine topics like independence, control, and the challenges women face

Objective of study The goal of this study is to closely examine how women are presented in Anand Neelakantan's stories, focusing on their roles, how they are represented, and how they connect to larger themes like power, influence and identity. We will examine how women's experiences and chances are affected by their social status, such as caste, class, and family background. Additionally, we will evaluate how women's stories fit into Neelakantan's writing style, including the way he tells the story, develops the plot, and explores themes. This research will also look at how Neelakantan's retellings of myths challenge old stories and present new views on what it means to be female. By doing this, we hope to gain a deeper understanding of women's stories in Anand Neelakantan's fictional world and their importance in literature, gender studies, and discussions about culture.

Review of Literature Anand Neelakantan's novels offer a fresh feminist reinterpretation of women in Indian mythology which challenge traditional gender roles. Characters like Sita, Kunti, Draupadi,

and Sivagami are portrayed as complex, powerful figures who influence political and social events. Scholars highlight how Neelakantan disrupts passive depictions of these women, presenting them as active agents of change. His female characters are often shown to navigate the intersections of caste, class, and morality, defying patriarchal constraints. Their political acumen and resilience are central themes, as they challenge stereotypes and reclaim Power. Neelakantan also explores female solidarity, showing both collaboration and conflict among women in their struggle for power. Neelakantan disrupts these portrayals by giving these women power, depth, and moral complexity. In her analysis, Bose (2018) argues that Neelakantan presents these mythological women as leaders in their own right, whose choices and decisions influence the larger narrative. Similarly, Nair (2019) examines how the female antagonists in Neelakantan's works move beyond the limited, one-dimensional roles assigned to them in the original texts, and emerge as powerful to make the change who actively shape political and social landscapes.

Methodology To conduct this research we used primary and secondary data from online and offline sources

Analysis

Draupadi is a strong and complex female character in the Indian mythological work Mahabharata. She is also known as Panchali. In Anand Neelakantan's Ajaya series, this tells the story from Duryodhana's point of view in which Draupadi is shown with great details, emphasizing her strength, wisdom, choices, feelings, impact and political skills.

Draupadi was the daughter of King Drupada from Panchala. She was born from a sacred fire during a yajna. She married the five Pandava after Arjuna won her in a swayamvara. Draupadi had five sons, each from a different husband, known as the Upapandavas. Her marriage to the Pandavas was very important in the Mahabharata story and led to the start of the Kurukshetra war. Draupadi's decisions frequently hold significant importance, extending to both personal and political dimensions. Her decision to seek revenge against the Kauravas following her severe humiliation is motivated by a profound commitment to honor and justice. She displays a reluctance to forgive and seeks justice, which profoundly impacts the actions of the Pandavas. Draupadi was very wise and always knows for right and wrong. She doubts the ethics of the Pandavas and Kauravas, especially when they play a risky dice game, she questioned whether Yudhishtira should gamble her after losing himself. Her ability to see unfairness makes her very clear-minded, often helping her husbands make good choices. "Draupadi's inner fire, her refusal to accept injustice, her dignity in defeat — they were qualities that transcended the limitations of her time." (Yuganta: The End of an Epoch 1967). Draupadi's strength comes from her beauty and boldness. She is rare in ancient stories for standing up to unfair treatment, even against her husbands. Her boldness leads to the Kurukshetra war, starting with her public shame over a dice game. Draupadi, a woman characterized by unwavering determination who exhibits a profound affection towards her husbands, a sentiment that is particularly pronounced in her love for Arjuna. Despite the complex relationships that arise from the shared marital status of her husbands, she remains loyal to each of them. Her affection extends to her children as well, with the loss of her sons during the war leading to profound sorrow. Nevertheless, her affections do not compromise her discernment, as she consistently places justice and the welfare of the Pandavas above her own personal interests. Draupadi makes political choices to seek justice and fix her family's reputation. After a dice game, she was known for fighting back and demanding revenge, leading the Pandavas into war. She knows her actions have political consequences and uses her power to guide events. Draupadi's decisions show her deep understanding of power and her dedication to doing what's right. "Perhaps it was I who was responsible for the war, not because of the events of that fateful day, but because of how I allowed my resentment to simmer in my heart." (The Palace of Illusions, 2008).

In the Ajaya series by Anand Neelakantan, Draupadi is shown as a strong woman whose decisions and personal views greatly affect the story. Her strong sense of justice and her power to sway others make her a legendary and influential figure in Indian mythology.

Sita and her birth is frequently attributed to divinity. It is said that she was discovered by King Janaka of Mithila while engaged in agricultural activities as part of a sacrificial ritual, thereby giving the name of "Daughter of the Earth" or Bhumiija. Assigned to the royal lineage, she was celebrated for her allure, intellect, and elegance. Her emergence from the earth is emblematic of purity, a quality she is frequently linked with the goddess Lakshmi, the spouse of Vishnu, suggesting her celestial lineage. In Anand Neelakantan's novel *Asura: Tale of the Vanquished*, Sita plays a significant role, particularly in her interactions with Ravana and her experiences in the kingdom of Lanka. Anand Neelakantan presents Sita as a multi-dimensional character with her own opinions, desires and struggles. Unlike traditional portrayals of Sita as a passive and honorable wife, Neelakantan's Sita is presented as a woman with her ambitions and convictions. Sita's interactions with Ravana are central to the novel's narrative rather than being portrayed solely as Rama's wife. Sita forms a complex relationship with Ravana, who sees her as a symbol of his desire for power and domination. Sita's interactions with Ravana challenge traditional notions of morality and loyalty which adds depth to her

character. "I was more than the woman who suffered in silence, more than the queen who was wronged. I was the forest woman, I was the mother, I was the woman who chose exile over a throne." *The Forest of Enchantments* (2019). Throughout the novel Sita demonstrates resilience and control in the face of adversity. Even though she was captive in Lanka, she doesn't give in to sadness and keeps her self-respect and resilience. She refused Ravana proposal which shows her strong dedication to her beliefs, her inner power and strength. Sita's character also serves as a voice for the marginalized and oppressed within the kingdom of Lanka. Through her interactions with other characters, including the asura community she sheds light on the injustices and inequalities that exist within Ravana's kingdom, challenging readers to question conventional notions of good and evil. Her role as a catalyst for change and transformation within the narrative reflects broader philosophical and existential questions explored throughout the novel. Sita's narrative is deeply imbued with symbolism, often seen as the quintessential embodiment of female resilience and endurance. She perseveres through profound trials, steadfast in her virtue and dedication. Her unwavering love for her husband, her moral strength in the face of daunting challenges, and her ultimate act of self determination render her a multifaceted and inspirational figure. Sita's strength lies not in her submission, but in her choices. She chooses the forest, chooses to raise her sons alone, and ultimately, chooses her own freedom by returning to the earth." *Sita: An Illustrated Retelling of the Ramayana* (2013). For centuries, Sita has been celebrated not only as a symbol of perfect womanhood but also as a testament to the power found in patience, integrity, and righteousness. Her tale continues to spark conversations about gender, duty, and morality, with interpretations varying across different cultures and eras.

Mandodari is a significant character in the Hindu epic Ramayana. She is the wife of Ravana, the king of Lanka and the primary antagonist of the epic. Mandodari is often presented as a woman of great wisdom, virtue and strength, contrasting with the character of her husband. Despite Ravana's flaws and his abduction of Sita, Mandodari remains loyal to him and tries to advise him against his acts of betrayal. She is known for her intelligence and her attempts to counsel Ravana and urge him to release Sita and avoid conflict with Lord Rama, but her efforts often go unheard. Mandodari is also known for her devotion to dharma and her deep understanding of moral principles. Her character adds depth to the narrative of the Ramayana, highlighting the complexities of human relationships and the consequences of one's actions. In some versions of the Ramayana, Mandodari is portrayed as the mother of Ravana's son Indrajit who plays a crucial role in the later stages of the war between Rama and Ravana. "In many folk Ramayanas, it is believed that Mandodari is a nymph. She is some kind of a celestial creature. She is given by the Rakshasa called Maya, and Lanka is part of her dowry. She's the mother of Meghanadha, Atikaya and Akshay Kumar." *Tales of Mandodari* by Devvatt Pattnayak.

Tara is a crucial figure in the Indian epic Ramayana, renowned for her wisdom, diplomatic skills, and unwavering devotion. She was introduced in the *Kishkindha Kanda*, where she plays a vital role in the political intrigues and conflicts involving the monkey tribe. As the wife of Vali, the formidable king of Kishkindha, and the mother of Angada, Tara's life is often overshadowed by the ongoing strife between her husband and his brother, Sugriva. Despite these challenges, Tara emerges as a symbol of strength, intelligence and profound emotional depth. During the time of the churning of the ocean, Bali defeated the Daityas who came to fight because of the difference of opinion. The gods were happy with Bali for defeating the Daityas and they gave him Tara as his wife. Tara is presented as a wise and insightful counselor, often providing valuable advice to her husband Vali and later to Sugriva. Her wisdom helps shape the decisions of the Vanara kings and contributes to their success in the battle against Ravana. Despite being caught midst of the conflict between Vali and Sugriva, Tara maintains her independence and self-reliance. She does not hesitate to express her opinions or challenge the actions of the male characters when necessary. Tara demonstrates remarkable resilience in the face of adversity, particularly after the death of her husband Vali. Despite her grief, she remains steadfast in her support for Sugriva and continues to play an active role in the affairs of the Vanara kingdom. Tara exhibits political acumen and strategic thinking throughout the Ramayana. She understands the complexities of power dynamics and alliances, and her counsel proves invaluable in navigating the challenges posed by Ravana and his forces. Tara is portrayed as a compassionate and empathetic character, capable of understanding the emotions and motivations of those around her. Her empathy towards Sugriva and willingness to forgive his past transgressions exemplify her compassionate nature. Tara plays a crucial role in reconciling the differences between Vali and Sugriva, ultimately paving the way for Sugriva's ascension to the throne. Her diplomacy and mediation skills contribute to the stability and unity of the Vanara kingdom.

Kunti was the mother of the Pandavas who plays a significant role in the Mahabharata, she has influential power in various ways throughout the epic. Kunti's influence as a mother is profound, shaping the destinies of her sons and impacting the course of the epic. She instills values of righteousness, duty and loyalty in the Pandavas, guiding them through their trials and tribulations. Kunti demonstrates political acumen and strategic thinking in her interactions with other characters. She advises her sons on matters of

diplomacy, governance and warfare. She played a crucial role in their efforts to reclaim their kingdom and establish their rightful place in society. At times, Kunti resorts to manipulative tactics to achieve her goals and protect her son's interests. For example, she encourages Yudhishtira to gamble in the game of dice and she knows the impact risks involved, to uphold their honor and dignity. Kunti's willingness to make personal sacrifices for the sake of her sons is evident throughout the Mahabharata. She endures hardships and challenges with resilience and fortitude, always placing the well-being of her children above her desires and ambitions. Kunti seeks the guidance and support of Krishna during times of crisis, and Krishna, in turn, offers her solace, wisdom, and protection. Kunti's legacy extends beyond her lifetime, shaping the actions and decisions of future generations. Her teachings and examples continue to inspire characters throughout the Mahabharata and beyond. Overall, Kunti's role and power in the Mahabharata are characterized by her maternal love, wisdom and political astuteness. As a central figure in the epic narrative, she embodies the complexities of human nature and the profound impact of maternal guidance and influence on the course of history.

Shivagami is the leading female character of bahubali series. In Anand Neelakantan's novel "The Rise of Sivagami", Shivagami's character is presented as a formidable and influential figure, exerting power in various ways throughout the novel. Shivagami possesses keen political acumen and strategic intelligence which allow her to navigate the complex power dynamics of the Mahishmathi kingdom. She is adept at manipulating situations to her advantage and understanding the motivations of those around her. As the queen mother and regent of Mahishmathi, Shivagami holds significant authority and commands respect from both allies and adversaries. She exercises her power with a firm hand, making decisive decisions for the betterment of the kingdom. She is known for her sense of justice and compassion. She prefers to intervene on behalf of those who are marginalized or mistreated. Shivagami's character is defined by her relentless pursuit of justice and righteousness. She is willing to challenge corrupt systems and confront injustice, even if it means risking her safety or reputation. Shivagami's influence extends beyond her lifetime, shaping the destiny of Mahishmathi and leaving a lasting legacy for future generations. Her actions and decisions have far-reaching consequences, impacting the course of history in the fictional world of the Bahubali series. Shivagami's power is also portrayed through her willingness to make personal sacrifices for the greater good. She puts the interests of the kingdom above her own desires and ambitions, demonstrating a sense of duty and selflessness in her leadership. Sivagami emerges as a complex and compelling character in Anand Neelakantan's "The Rise of Sivagami," embodying the qualities of strength, intelligence, and compassion. Her portrayal reflects the complexities of power and leadership, highlighting the challenges and responsibilities that come with wielding authority in a tumultuous world. A key aspect of Neelakantan's portrayal of women is their intersection with caste and class struggles. The Rise of Sivagami, Sivagami's journey is marked not only by her gender but by her low-caste origins, which add layers of complexity to her ambitions. Desai (2020) examines how Neelakantan intertwines caste and class oppression with gender, suggesting that his female characters often confront not only gender-based discrimination but also the limitations imposed by their socio-economic status. Neelakantan's women are seen as navigating these intersections with moral ambiguity, challenging the traditional binary understanding of good and evil.

Conclusion In conclusion, the examination of various female characters across Anand Neelakantan's fictional universe reveals a common thread of empowerment, resilience. Through his novels, including "Asura: Tale of the Vanquished," "The Rise of Sivagami," and others, Neelakantan reimagines traditional narratives, bring forth the diverse and complex narratives of femininity. These female characters are not relegated to peripheral roles or one-dimensional stereotypes but are presented as dynamic individuals with their ambitions and strengths. From Draupadi's assertiveness and defiance of patriarchal norms to Sita's resilience and compassion, from Tara's wisdom and political acumen to Kunti's maternal influence and strategic prowess, and finally, to Shivagami's formidable leadership and sense of justice, each character embodies different facets of feminine power and influence. Through a thematic examination of these characters, Neelakantan challenges traditional gender norms, redefines femininity, and contributes to broader conversations about empowerment and representation in literature. The exploration of feminine narratives in Neelakantan's works invites deeper analysis of the roles, representations, and complexities of women within mythological retellings and historical fiction, shedding light on the evolving roles of women in contemporary literature and society. In essence, Anand Neelakantan's portrayal of female characters reflects a nuanced understanding of gender dynamics, power, and resilience, highlighting the significance of reimagining femininity in narratives that transcend time and tradition. Anand Neelakantan's novels offer a transformative lens on the roles of women in mythology. By positioning female characters as central figures in political, social, and moral dilemmas, Neelakantan shifts the narrative focus away from male-dominated epic tales to highlight women's agency and power. His works challenge traditional stereotypes, addressing issues of caste, class, and gender intersectionality in the process. Scholars widely acknowledge Neelakantan's feminist reinterpretation as a significant contribution to modern Indian literature, providing nuanced

and empowering portrayals of women who not only survive but shape the world around them.

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